

ARAB- ISRAEL UPRISING AND US ROLE AS A CATALYST

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Abstract:

Historically Washington has viewed Israel as a crucial political and economic ally in the oil-rich Middle East, and has provided Israel with the highest amount of financial and military assistance of any other foreign country. The Arab-Israeli conflict, a deeply rooted and complicated struggle, has shaped the geopolitics of the Middle East for over a century. Rooted in historical, religious, and territorial disputes, the conflict mainly involves the Israel and various Arab nations, as well as the Palestinian people, who seek sovereignty and self-determination. The role of the United States in this conflict has been pivotal, acting both as a reliable ally of Israel and as a mediator in peace efforts. Often seen as a catalyst, U.S. involvement has significantly influenced the dynamics of the conflict, shaping the course of negotiations, regional relations, and international responses. This introduction aims to explore the complex interaction between U.S. actions and the ongoing Arab-Israeli tensions, highlighting the challenges and implications of U.S. diplomacy in one of the world's most enduring conflicts.

Keyword: Palestine, Arab, US, Israel, Conflict, Catalyst

Introduction

The Israeli-Palestinian conflict is rooted in a century-long territorial dispute over the Holy Land, a Middle Eastern region with great religious and historical significance to Christians, Jews, and Muslims. Increasing numbers of Jews began moving to Ottoman Palestine - a predominately Arab region—following the 1896 publication of Theodor Herzl's 'The Jewish State' which promoted the idea of a haven for Jews in their ancient homeland to escape anti-Semitism in Europe. The migration accelerated after the Holocaust of World War II, in which Nazi Germany killed six million Jews. It is widely believed that the Israeli invasion of Lebanon in

the summer of 1982 opened a new chapter in the US -Israel “special relationship”. Historically Washington has viewed Israel as a crucial political and economic ally in the oil-rich Middle East, and has provided Israel with the highest amount of financial and military assistance of any other foreign country. The US remains committed to safeguarding Israel’s military dominance in the region so that further aggression resulting from the imbalance of force is not unlikely. The Arabs of Palestine were overwhelmingly opposed to a Jewish state which often led to their dispossession from their lands. “They had not been consulted at any level in the preparation of European plans for the disposal of their homeland and felt in no way bound peaceably to accept their implementation” (Lucas, 1975).

In November 1947, the General Assembly of the United Nations recommended the partition of mandatory Palestine into a Jewish and an Arab state. The recommendation was accepted by the majority of the Zionist movement though not by Begin’s terrorist army (the Irgun Tsvai Leumi) and LEHI (the Stern Group), the terrorist force commanded by the current Foreign Minister, Yitzhak Shamir and rejected with near unanimity by the Arabs of Palestine. General Assembly resolutions are considered to be non-binding; Israel, for example, holds the world record for rejection of subsequent ones. The US remained ambivalent for a time preferring a trusteeship until Truman recognized the Jewish state established in May 1948 (Skyces, 2022, p.337). For a contemporary record of Irgun-LEHI terrorism in December 1947, see *Peace in the Middle East?*, pp. 64-5.

Israeli policy toward the settlements in the West Bank has undergone various changes over the years, reflecting the divergent political views of decision makers, the relative weight of various interest groups active in this field, and developments in the international arena. The national unity government headed by Levi Eshkol was established shortly before the outbreak of war in June 1967. During the months immediately following the war, this government did not have any clear policy regarding Israeli settlement in the West Bank. The initial inclination of most of the members of the government was to hold the territory as a bargaining chip for future negotiations. Accordingly, they opposed plans to establish civilian settlements in this area. However, these inclinations were rapidly eroded, due both to the pressures exerted by various interest groups and as

the result of initiatives from within the government. As early as September 1967, Kfar Ezyon became the first settlement to be established in the West Bank. It was established because of the pressure of a group of settlers, some of whom were relatives of the residents of the original community of Kfar Ezyon, which was abandoned and destroyed during the 1948 war (Rich & Duyvestyn, 2012, p. 228). The unity government's policy on "East Jerusalem" was different. Immediately after the war, the Government applied Israeli law to extensive areas to the north, east and south of West Jerusalem, which were annexed to the Municipality of Jerusalem. The government began a rapid process to build settlements in these areas. Its goal was to prevent any challenge to Israel's sovereignty over them and to impede initiatives leading to an Israeli withdrawal from these areas (Rubenberg, 1989, p. 28). The issue of Israeli settlements in the Occupied Territories (West Bank, Gaza, and East Jerusalem) has long been a subject of dispute between the United States and Israel. Their continued existence presents a major challenge to bringing peace to Israel with its Arab neighbors. Moreover, many perceptions of this issue in the United States are uninformed and lead to continued US support of an expanding settlement enterprise that is clearly at odds with US national interests in the Middle East. Indeed, the continually expanding settlements in the West Bank are also against the long-term security interests of the state of Israel. Because of a pro-Israel bias in the American mainstream media, it should not come as a surprise that most Americans possess pro-Israel views, and by pro-Israel, this means pro-Israeli right. Other commonly held perceptions are the belief that Israel is the only democracy in the Middle East and the best ally of the United States in the region; that Israel is a peace-loving country which seeks nothing but to live in peace with its neighbors; that a second Holocaust is inevitable if Israel does not do all it can to defend itself; that Palestinians kill Israelis because of a fanatical hatred of Jews and because the Qur'an tells them to do so; Palestinians are taught to hate Jews from childhood; Palestinians don't kill Jews because of the military occupation, proven by the fact that they often target civilians in Israel instead of military targets inside the occupied territories; and that Arabs cannot be trusted. If Arabs cannot be trusted, concluding a peace treaty with the Palestinians would only put Tel Aviv in closer missile range. Many of these perceptions have kernels of truth in them; others are simply propaganda. Without discussing each perception (which would require a full-length paper in itself), I will attempt to pierce

through the cloud of media distortion and explain what is really occurring in the region (Pashakhanlou, 2014, p. 19).

The 1948 War of Independence ended with Israel signing separate armistice agreements with Egypt, Transjordan, Lebanon, and Syria. Israel had achieved a great victory, having established its new borders on 78% of Mandatory Palestine (not including Transjordan after its independence in 1946) along what is now known as the “Green Line”. Transjordan remained in control of the West Bank and East Jerusalem, and Egypt remained in control of the Gaza Strip. East Jerusalem, the West Bank and the Gaza Strip would then remain outside of Israel’s control until Israel’s victory in the 1967 Six Day War. Between June 5 and June 10, Israel defeated Egypt, Jordan, and Syria and occupied the Sinai Peninsula, the Gaza Strip, the West Bank, East Jerusalem, and the Golan Heights. From the beginning, the United States sought a ceasefire in order to prevent an Arab defeat bad enough to force the Soviet Union to intervene. U.S. officials were also concerned about alienating pro-Western Arab regimes, especially after Egypt and several other Arab states accused the United States of helping Israel and broke diplomatic relations. Yet after June 5, the administration did not also demand an immediate Israeli pullback from the territories it had occupied. U.S. officials believed that in light of the tenuous nature of the prewar armistice regime, they should not force Israel to withdraw unless peace settlements were put into place. On the other hand, returning to the importance of settlements in the overall Israeli strategy, David Ben-Gurion wrote in his *Memoirs* that “Israel is ours in the Twentieth Century not because we fought wars over it, but because we settled it” (Zimberg, 1980).

The Middle East has long been of central importance to the United States as successive administrations pursued a broad set of interrelated goals including securing vital energy resources, staving off Soviet and Iranian influence, ensuring the survival and security of Israel and Arab allies, countering terrorism, promoting democracy, and reducing refugee flows. Correspondingly, the United States has sought to resolve the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, which has been a major driver of regional dynamics, with an eye toward obtaining these strategic objectives while balancing its support for Israel and pushing for broader regional stability. The United States has been a central player in the Israeli-

Palestinian conflict for more than half a century. It became involved shortly after World War II, joining the United Kingdom in a 1946 inquiry that recommended one hundred thousand Holocaust survivors relocate to Palestine, which would be neither a Jewish nor an Arab state. The United States then became the first country to recognize Israel as a sovereign nation in 1948 (Gultom & Miftah, 2024, pp. 38-49).

US consider Israel a strategic base for U.S. interests, and the mutual interests of the two countries are the secret behind America's support for Israel. The U.S. strategy cannot be separated from Israel's in any way, as the elements of strategic planning for both countries are interconnected to a large degree. The U.S. believes that the safety and security of Israel guarantees the stability of the region and the protection of U.S. interests there. During the early years of Israel's establishment, the U.S. strained every nerve to serve Israel, as it was hostile to Soviet expansion and a custodian of U.S. interests in the Middle East. Therefore, the U.S. administration expressed its desire for guardianship over Palestine from the United Nations (UN) in March 1948, so as to give the Zionist entity international legitimacy. However, the UN did not agree to a temporary guardianship, which is why the U.S. decided to support UN Resolution 181 –the “Partition Resolution (Spiegel, 1985, p. 34).”

The close relations between the United States and Israel stem from shared cultural bonds, strategic ties, and well-organized pro-Israel sentiment in the United States. Israel also has potential strategic value as a friend in the Gulf, which is an important but unstable region. However, because of historical tension between the surrounding Arab states and Israel and disputes over territory between the Israelis and the Palestinians, America's relations with Israel have hindered U.S. military efforts and complicated U.S. relations with Arab states in the Gulf. For example, during Operation Desert Storm, the United States feared that Israeli participation in the war would split the anti-Iraq coalition that existed among the United States and several Arab Gulf states. Consequently, the U.S.-led coalition devoted considerable resources to defending Israel against Iraqi missile attacks instead of letting Israel defend itself. At the beginning of the Gulf war in 1991, President George H.W. Bush declared solving the Arab-Israeli conflict among his postwar goals. On March 6, 1991, he outlined a framework for peace based on U.N. Security Council Resolutions 242 and 338 and the

principle of "land for peace." Secretary of State James Baker organized a peace conference in Madrid in October 1991 that launched almost a decade of the "Oslo process" to achieve peace. It continued under President William Clinton, who asserted that only the region's leaders can make peace and vowed to be their partner. With the Hebron Protocol of 1997, however, the United States seemed to become an indispensable and expected party to Israeli-Palestinian talks. Clinton mediated the 1998 Wye River Memorandum and personally led negotiations at Camp David in 2000. The George W. Bush Administration initially sought a less prominent role, and Secretary of State Colin Powell did not appoint a special Middle East envoy. After the September 11, 2001, terrorist attacks, the Administration focused on the peace process mainly as part of the war on terrorism. Secretary of State Condoleezza Rice also did not name a special envoy, asserting, "Not every effort has to be an American effort. It is extremely important that the parties themselves are taking responsibility (Gearan, 2005)." She encouraged Israelis and Palestinians to act, but personally mediated a November 2005 accord to reopen the border crossing between Gaza and Egypt after Israel's withdrawal from Gaza. In 2007, she engaged again partly in order to elicit the support of moderate Sunni Arab governments to thwart the rise of Iranian influence. Those governments see resolution of the Palestinian issue as a key to regional stability and to denying Iran opportunities for destabilizing actions.

After the first Gulf war, in 1991, a new peace process consisting of bilateral negotiations between Israel and the Palestinians, Jordan, Syria, and Lebanon achieved mixed results. Milestones included the Israeli-Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) Declaration of Principles (DOP) of September 13, 1993, providing for Palestinian empowerment and some territorial control, the Israeli-Jordanian peace treaty of October 26, 1994, and the Interim Self-Rule in the West Bank or Oslo II accord of September 28, 1995, which led to the formation of the Palestinian Authority (PA) to govern the West Bank and Gaza Strip. However, Israeli-Syrian negotiations were intermittent and difficult, and postponed indefinitely in 2000. Israeli-Lebanese negotiations also were unsuccessful, leading Israel to withdraw unilaterally from south Lebanon on May 24, 2000. President Clinton held a summit with Israeli and Palestinian leaders at Camp David on final status issues that July, but they did not produce an

accord. A Palestinian uprising or intifada began in September. On February 6, 2001, Ariel Sharon was elected Prime Minister of Israel, and rejected steps taken at Camp David and afterwards. On April 30, 2003, the United States, the U.N., European Union, and Russia (known as the “Quartet”) presented a “Road Map” to Palestinian statehood. It has not been implemented. Israel unilaterally withdrew from the Gaza Strip and four small settlements in the West Bank in August 2005. On January 9, 2005, Mahmud Abbas had become President of the PA. The victory of Hamas which Israel and the United States consider a terrorist group, in the January 2006 Palestinian parliamentary elections complicated prospects for peace as the United States, Israel and the Quartet would not deal with a Hamas-led government until it disavowed violence, recognized Israel, and accepted prior Israeli-Palestinian accords (Migdalovitz, 2010).

Key Events and U.S. Involvement

- **The Suez Crisis (1956):** The U.S. played a crucial role in resolving the Suez Crisis, where Israel, the United Kingdom, and France invaded Egypt following the nationalization of the Suez Canal. The U.S., under President Dwight D. Eisenhower, pressurized these allies to withdraw, showcasing its influence and prioritizing stability in the region over immediate strategic gains.
- **The Six-Day War (1967):** This war saw Israel capture significant territories, including the Gaza Strip, Golan Heights, West Bank, and Sinai Peninsula. The U.S. provided diplomatic support to Israel during and after the war, leading to a shift in the regional balance of power. The war's outcome laid the groundwork for ongoing disputes over territories, particularly regarding the Palestinian issue.
- **Camp David Accords (1978):** The U.S. under President Jimmy Carter, successfully brokered peace between Israel and Egypt, the first Arab state to recognize Israel. The accords led to Israel's withdrawal from the Sinai Peninsula and established a framework for peace that has influenced subsequent negotiations.
- **Oslo Accords (1993):** The U.S. facilitated secret negotiations between Israel and the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO), leading to the Oslo Accords. This was a significant step towards a two-state solution, with the establishment of the Palestinian

Authority and mutual recognition between Israel and the PLO. However, the process ultimately stalled, with both sides unable to resolve key issues like the status of Jerusalem, refugees, and borders.

- **The Second Intifada (2000-2005):** This period of intense Israeli-Palestinian violence led to a significant hardening of positions on both sides. The U.S. under President George W. Bush initially focused on counter-terrorism post-9/11, with less emphasis on the peace process. However, Bush later proposed the "Roadmap for Peace," which sought to establish a Palestinian state but faced numerous obstacles.ⁱ
- **The Abraham Accords (2020):** Under President Donald Trump, the U.S. brokered normalization agreements between Israel and several Arab states, including the UAE, Bahrain, Sudan, and Morocco. These accords marked a significant shift in the regional dynamics, as some Arab states moved towards recognizing Israel without resolving the Palestinian issue, which has been a departure from the Arab Peace Initiative.

Broader Implications of U.S. Involvement

- **Shift in Arab-Israeli Relations:** U.S. involvement has contributed to shifts in Arab-Israeli relations, with some Arab states moving towards normalization with Israel. This has altered the traditional Arab consensus, which linked peace with Israel to the resolution of the Palestinian issue.
- **Impact on Palestinian-Israeli Peace Process:** While the U.S. has attempted to mediate peace between Israel and the Palestinians, its strong support for Israel has often been viewed as biased by Palestinians and many in the Arab world. This perception has sometimes undermined U.S. efforts to act as an honest broker in the peace process.
- **Regional Stability and Instability:** U.S. involvement has had mixed effects on regional stability. While it has helped broker peace agreements like the Camp David Accords, it has also been involved

ⁱRetrieved 13th August, 2024 from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Second_Intifada

in actions that have contributed to instability, such as the Iraq War in 2003, which had far-reaching consequences for the region (Quero & Dessì, 2021, pp. 311-30).

Conclusion

The United States has been intensely involved in the Arab-Israeli conflict for decades, acting as both a mediator and a supporter of Israel and a provider of aid and support. Its role as a catalyst in the conflict has been shaped by a complex mix of strategic interests, diplomatic efforts, and regional dynamics. While the U.S. has contributed to major breakthroughs, such as peace treaties between Israel and some Arab states, its involvement has also been a source of controversy and tension, particularly regarding the unresolved Palestinian issue. The future of U.S. involvement will likely continue to influence the prospects for peace and stability in the region.

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